

AI·EFFECT

Artificial Intelligence Experimentation Facility
For the Energy sector

D6.3 Initial Dissemination and Communication Plan

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Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
OA	Open Access
OER	Open Educational Resource
TEF	Testing and Experimentation Facility
TG	Target Group
TSO	Transmission System Operator
WP	Work Package

Consortium

Number	Legal Name	Acronym	Country
01	EPRI Europe DAC (Coordinator)	EEU	IE
02	Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores, Tecnologia e Ciência	INESC TEC	PT
03	Danmarks Tekniske Universitet	DTU	DK
04	Technische Universiteit Delft	TU Delft	NL
05	Institut de Recherche Technologique SystemX	IRTSX	FR
06	Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e. V.	Fraunhofer	DE
07	Rheinisch-Westfaelische Technische Hochschule Aachen	RWTH	DE
08	IKIM LTD.	IKIM	IE
09	Maynooth University	NUIM	IE
10	DNV AS	DNV	NO
11	EnliteAI GmbH	ENLITE	AT
12	Watt-IS S.A.	WATT-IS	PT
13	Cooperativa Eléctrica do Vale D'Este CRL	CEVE	PT
14	Bornholms Varme A/S	BHV	DK
15	ENEL GRIDS S.R.L	ENEL	IT
16	E Distribucion redes Digitales (Affiliated Entity)	EDRD	ES
17	Hertie School Gemeinnutzige GMBH	HERTIE	DE
18	Center Danmark Drift APS	CDK	DK
19	Tennet TSO BV (Associated Partner)	TENNET	NL

Table 1 List of AI-EFFECT partners

Executive Summary

The EU-funded AI-EFFECT project aims to enhance access to the tools and facilities necessary for developing, testing, and validating AI solutions in the energy sector. To achieve this, the project will establish an innovative European testing and experimentation facility, composed of distributed, virtually connected existing European facilities. Additionally, it will develop a digital platform that ensures interoperability, scalability, and flexibility for users and resources.

The AI-EFFECT project will be developed through four distinct phases, aligned with its objectives and incorporating six work packages (WP). WP6, which focuses on Project Management, Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication, addresses the management of the project, including the communication and stakeholder engagement activities.

This deliverable D6.3, the Initial Dissemination and Communication Plan, outlines all actions to communicate and disseminate AI-EFFECT's results beyond the consortium. This plan aims to maximize contributions to the European energy industry and attract key stakeholders to benefit from AI-EFFECT's solutions. It identifies target audiences and key stakeholders, defines tailored messages and concrete, measurable objectives for each group, and sets up dedicated communication channels and tools. The plan also introduces the actions taken up to Month 6 and outlines the pathway to monitor the impact of the communication and dissemination strategies. Finally, the communication plan is divided into four different campaigns, consistent with the four separate phases of the project described in the project methodology to leverage project awareness and impact.

Introduction

As the digital age transforms the energy landscape, the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and critical energy infrastructure is set to boost efficiency, resilience, and sustainability.

The AI-EFFECT project (Artificial Intelligence Experimentation Facility For the Energy seCTor) is an European funded project, aiming to address:

- The need to link utilities that have data streams and datasets and major challenges to the AI industry and research communities who have the tools and capabilities to solve the utility challenges.
- The need for a consistent, standardised approach to development of trustworthy AI for the energy sector.
- The need to standardise and certify solutions based on a security and risk framework, governed by law.

AI-EFFECT will establish a European Testing and Experimentation Facility (TEF) for AI applications in the energy sector, enabling development, testing, and validation at various stages. It will virtually connect existing European computer and lab facilities through a digital platform, ensuring interoperability, scalability, and secure data exchange.

AI-EFFECT involves research and industry organisations from across Europe with a wide range of knowledge and complementary expertise to deliver the ambitious project objectives. The Consortium consists of 19 partners from nine countries (eight Member States and one Associated Country).

To achieve the primary objectives and expected outcomes, the AI-EFFECT project will be developed through four separate phases, mapped to the objectives, and incorporating six work packages. WP6 Project Management, Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication, addresses the management of the project and all the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation activities of AI-EFFECT. WP6 has the following objectives:

- 1) Coordinate the actions of participants and monitor the progress of project goals to ensure the delivery of results in a timely, cost-effective way;
- 2) Financial and administrative management, being a reliable interface to the EC, the external stakeholders and the public at large;
- 3) Identification and mitigation of project risks by performing effective risk management, managing the project IP;
- 4) Ensure maximum project visibility and impact by efficiently communicating project innovations;
- 5) Promote synergies with the energy industry, such as system operators, retailers and producers, as well as with the scientific community, including organizations active in related projects to combine efforts and accelerate dissemination;
- 6) Identify the best exploitation of the project results during and after the project;
- 7) Organise a constant dialogue with the relevant stakeholders.

Under this WP, tasks 6.3 and 6.4 specifically address Communication and Dissemination (C&D).

Task 6.3: Design and Implementation of Communication and Dissemination Activities aims to ensure engaging and impactful communications, active dissemination of project results, and systematic outreach to the most relevant audiences. This task includes selecting the main communication channels, defining tailored messages to key stakeholders, defining C&D activities and key performance indicators for those.

Task 6.4: Stakeholder Engagement, Community Building, Standardization, and Coordination with Other European Initiatives aims to engage key stakeholders (e.g., end-users, technology developers) throughout the project's duration. This activity will be closely coordinated with all work packages to define the best engagement approaches for each stakeholder. Collaboration will be fostered among policymakers, researchers, standardization bodies, and industry stakeholders to co-design frameworks that incentivize, boost, and support the adoption of AI-powered tools and solutions in the energy sector. This collaborative approach ensures that policies are well-informed, practical, and aligned with the needs of all stakeholders.

AI-EFFECT will establish knowledge-sharing initiatives, such as webinars, conferences, and online forums, to facilitate dialogue and information exchange among policymakers, researchers, industry stakeholders, and citizens. These initiatives will provide opportunities for continuous learning, dissemination of best

practices, and networking among stakeholders, fostering a collaborative ecosystem for policy development and implementation.

Table 2 sets out the workplan for the C&D for the entire duration of the project.

Table 2 Communication and Dissemination Work Plan

Deliverable	Title	Objective	WP	Lead	Type	Diss. Level	Month
D6.3	Initial dissemination and Communication Plan	Initial AI-EFFECT Dissemination and Communication Plan	WP6	EEU	R	PU	M6
D6.4	Dissemination, communication, and outreach activities	Interim and final report on dissemination and communication activities, stakeholder’s engagement, and project’s outreach	WP6	EEU	R	PU	M18 M36
Milestone	Title	WP	Month	Description			
M6.1	Project identity and communication material ready	WP6	M3	The whole project identity material (logo, templates, website, social media, etc) is ready and adopted by the consortium.			

1. Communication and Dissemination Plan

Communication encompasses all activities aimed at disseminating AI-EFFECT's results beyond the consortium. These efforts are designed to maximize contributions to the European energy industry and attract key stakeholders to benefit from AI-EFFECT's solutions.

1.1. Communication Objectives

The core principle of AI-EFFECT's C&D activities is to leverage innovative results and key achievements to generate value within target communities and initiatives at the European level and beyond, with the aim to:

1. Raise awareness about the importance of an open distributed Testing and Experimentation Facility to boost the adoption of AI-based solutions in the energy sector;
2. Promote an understanding about the digital tools and technologies that are being developed;
3. Reach and inform the stakeholders of the project, especially the ones in the demonstration areas, while the project is being developed;
4. Ensure broad visibility of the project;
5. Contribute to the creation of synergies with other ongoing and future HorizonEU-supported actions, including other TEFs.

1.2. Key Audiences and Target Stakeholders

The analysis of the relevant stakeholders, starting from the already identified Target Groups (TGs) has been carried out and for each stakeholder group a dedicated approach and engagement strategy, including main messages and best communication channels, has been defined.

The project identified seven Target Groups (TG1-TG7) from potential stakeholders, as explained in Table 3.

Table 3 AI-EFFECT Target Audiences

Target Group	Description
TG1	Scientific Communities, R&D and Academia.
TG2	Energy Industry , including a) TG2.1: Energy Producers; b) TG2.2: Grid Owner/Operators (DSOs and TSOs); c) TG2.3: Energy Communities; d) TG2.4: Energy Retailers and Aggregators; e) TG2.5: Energy Service Companies (e.g., ESCOs) and Energy Efficiency Consultants; f) TG2.6: Other Energy Companies.
TG3	Non-profit Organisations , including a) TG3.1: System Operators Associations (e.g., ENTSO-E, EDSO); b) TG3.2: Consumer Organisations (e.g., ECC-Network); c) TG3.3: Digital Innovation Hubs; d) TG3.4: Environmental Organisations; e) TG3.5: Other Non-Profit.
TG4	Technology Providers , including Companies developing/providing Software (SW) platforms, Hardware (HW) devices, AI tools and applications, Communication networks, Data analytics tools, Cybersecurity solutions, and IoT devices.
TG5	General Public and Civil Society , including Individual Energy Consumers, Prosumers and Customers.
TG6	Policy Makers, Regulators and Public Authorities at European, National and Regional levels, including Government and Governmental Agencies.
TG7	Standardisation Bodies , including IEC, IEEE, ISO, UNE, CEN, and GBC.

The communication messages are designed to be clear and concise, emphasizing the significance and benefits of the AI-EFFECT project for each target audience. They aim to create a compelling narrative that conveys the project's potential long-term impact on the energy sector.

Table 4 presents the communications messages tailored to each stakeholder.

Table 4 Stakeholder Groups and respective messages

Stakeholder Groups	Messages
TG1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advancing AI Research: With AI-EFFECT, we are pushing the boundaries of AI research and innovation. • AI-EFFECT provides access to unique datasets and real and simulated testing environments for proof of concept of new AI methods, enabling R&D community to conduct robust and impactful research. • Leveraging open and high-quality datasets to conduct impactful research and achieve significant results. • Bridging the gap between academia and real-world applications by providing insights into the requirements for adopting AI tools in industry. • Contribute to open access, generalizable AI concepts, and share your unique use cases and datasets with AI-EFFECT to drive community-driven innovation.
TG2	<p>TG2.1 and TG2.2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At AI-EFFECT, we are leveraging advanced AI tools to ensure efficient and reliable grid management and resilience. • Build your processes to be smarter, sustainable and profitable with AI-EFFECT TEF. • Enabling energy producers to optimize their operations through AI-driven solutions, enhancing efficiency and sustainability. • The project’s testing facilities allow for the safe experimentation and validation of AI models, ensuring reliable and secure integration into existing systems. • Simplify the adoption of AI tools and services in your operations. • AI-EFFECT TEF can empower energy producers with predictive analytics to stay ahead in dynamic markets. <p>TG2.3:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promoting transparency and understandability of AI in energy management. • Facilitating community empowerment with clear and accessible AI solutions. • Empowering energy communities by offering AI solutions that enhance local energy management and sustainability. • AI-EFFECT collaborative framework supports the development of community-specific use cases, promoting energy independence and efficiency. <p>TG2.4:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing AI-driven strategies and tools to support sustainable and profitable energy management. <p>TG2.5:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI-EFFECT offers solutions designed to test the integration of AI tools and services within your business operations, ensuring they meet your needs effectively. • Supporting a wide range of energy companies in adopting AI technologies to address industry challenges. • AI-EFFECT comprehensive testing facilities and collaborative approach ensure that AI solutions are robust, secure, and scalable.

<p>TG3</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AI-EFFECT supports non-profits in advancing their missions through AI-driven energy solutions, ensuring that applications are developed with social and environmental considerations in mind. <p>TG3.1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> AI-EFFECT supports System Operators Associations to understand AI-related issues and advocate for fair, open markets <p>TG3.2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing transparent, ethical AI solutions focused on privacy and data security, benefiting consumer organizations and enhancing energy services. <p>TG3.3:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Navigate AI adoption and foster innovation by collaborating to collect member insights and drive policy changes that benefit the digital ecosystem. <p>TG3.4:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> AI-EFFECT advocates for responsible AI use, mindful of energy citizens' data and privacy, while promoting sustainable and environmentally friendly practices Leveraging AI to advance climate-neutral energy and transport transitions, supporting the development of green technologies and aligning with environmental goals.
<p>TG4</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Test and validate your AI tools in a controlled environment, with near-real data and models ensuring the reliability and effectiveness of your tools. Leverage our resources to develop innovative products that meet market demands, expanding your product portfolio with cutting-edge AI solutions. Gain access to a suite of tools designed to simplify the development of AI services, streamlining your development process. Benefit from established methodologies and KPIs for testing AI products, providing a structured approach to validate your solutions against industry standards. With AI-EFFECT TEF you can showcase your AI solutions through live demos, demonstrating the capabilities and benefits of your products to potential clients and stakeholders.
<p>TG5</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AI isn't a magic solution, but it brings valuable, step-by-step improvements. AI-EFFECT uses these advancements to make real progress in the energy sector, helping to make everyday life smarter, safer, and more efficient. With AI-EFFECT, AI can be safely tested in a controlled environment, providing the knowledge and confidence consumers need to trust AI. Improving everyday life by providing reliable and tested AI energy solutions, ensuring safer, more efficient, and sustainable energy use for all.
<p>TG6</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Providing a controlled environment, as outlined in the AI Act, for safely developing, testing, and validating AI systems, ensuring compliance with regulations, mitigates risks, and fosters innovation. AI-EFFECT developments will enhance policies, enforce best practices legally, and clarify AI responsibilities. Promoting harmonization of national regulations regarding AI data usage for consistent and effective governance.

TG7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitating AI Standardization: AI-EFFECT identifies gaps and provides best practice knowledge, crucial for building trust and ensuring consistent, reliable AI implementation. • Supporting the development of interoperable AI standards, ensuring seamless integration across different systems and platforms for a cohesive and efficient AI ecosystem. • Supporting responsible development and use of AI technologies through the delivery of ethical AI implementation guidelines. • Developing and certifying AI solutions for the energy sector, focusing on interoperability and security to support a unified energy framework.
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1.3. Communication Channels and Tools

The communication and dissemination approach and strategies can be split into three main bigger groups:

1. **Dissemination towards the scientific community, industry and civil society:** Dissemination towards Target Groups to maximizing the visibility of the outcomes. This will be done via a network of collaborations, online seminar offers, workshops, publications in scientific journals, presentations at conferences and university training, direct involvement of final users in the demonstration sites, contributions to standards and regulations.
1. **Communication towards other TEF:** Knowledge sharing about AI testing and validation, and ethical issues, through the organization of thematic events, workshops, and podcast episodes.
2. **Communication towards citizens:** Communicate project impacts and expected societal outcomes in plain English, highlighting the benefits of AI and its ethical and social dimensions via various media outlets and the project digital presence.

The messages and channels to use will be tailored to each stakeholder group.

Moreover, the consortium partners will leverage their respective networks to maximise the outreach toward a wide set of external stakeholders.

Table 5 summarizes main communication activities and channels used in the project, the targeted KPIs and impact achieved until M6.

Table 5 Main communication activities, channels and respective KPIs

Communication Activities and Channels	Measurable KPIs and Target	M6
Project Visual Identity: Including the development of a professional-quality project logo together with associated templates for all presentation and marketing collaterals and a service/project motto.	100% of communication materials will be compliant with the project's visual identity and branding.	100% of materials are compliant with the visual identity
Communication Material: Development of infographics, posters/rollups, and flyers/leaflets/postcards that will contain general project information, as well as best practices and ad-hoc information for events.	No. of distributed communication material: > 500 (copies distributed, including printing and download).	150 leaflets printed 1 roll up printed 13 downloads
Project Website: It includes all non-disclosure information about the project: general description, relevant publications, public deliverables,	Unique visitors: > 1500/year	Unique visitors: 270 Unique page visits: 556

partnerships, and events. The website will be updated bi-weekly.	Unique page visits: > 3.000/year No. of downloads: > 70/year	No. of downloads: 13
Social Media: The project will leverage social media platforms for real-time updates, engagement, and community building, especially LinkedIn, which will be critical in engaging with professionals at a European level and raising the profile of the initiative.	LinkedIn: No. of posts: 2 per month No. of impressions: > 300 per post No. of engagement (like/share/ comment): >10 per post	No. of posts: 3 per month No. of impressions: 800 on average per post No. of engagement: 22 on average per post
Newsletter: Stakeholders and a wider audience will be reached through newsletters presenting the project, its objectives, and findings.	No. of newsletters: 6 (2/year) No. of subscribers: > 100	Newsletter to be sent on M7
Technology brochure: Development of a brochure gathering key technical information about the technologies developed (factsheets and specifications).	No. of technical brochures: > 4	0
Promotional Videos: Promotional videos presenting the overall project and part of the tests carried out during the project duration will be prepared.	No. of videos: 3 No. of views: > 300/per video	1 video
Press Releases: press releases will be issued at key project milestones, or achievements, leading to several news pieces being published in international media outlets about the project.	No. of press releases: 8 No. of media insertions: > 25	3 press releases 7 media insertions
Joint Events, Workshops and Networking: Events organised by experts, researchers, clients, and industry audiences, where project partners will be invited to present their work and vision.	No. of events: 5 No. of participants: > 150	3 events 620 participants
Training Workshops and Webinars: They will target various stakeholder groups to inform them about benefits, best practices, and specific adaptations; for technical/managerial staff, but also public/consumers-oriented events.	No. of training workshops: > 3 No. of webinars: > 5 No. of participants: > 100	No workshops or webinars hosted so far.
Podcast: To building awareness, education and understanding about AI in Energy sector, as well as awareness of project progress and engagement among the target audience, especially organizations with varying levels of expertise and interest in the intersection of artificial intelligence and the energy sector.	No. of podcasts: 6 (2/year) No of downloads: >500 (total) Nb of subscribers: >50	First podcast episode will be recorded in April.

The monitoring and evaluation of C&D KPIs will be an ongoing process. Matomo Analytics will be utilized to assess website performance, while social media KPIs will be tracked using the native analytics tools of the respective platforms. Video performance data will be gathered from social media channels.

Additionally, the selected newsletter platform will offer in-depth analytics. A detailed log will be kept to document all activities carried out by consortium partners.

Ongoing monitoring will allow for strategy adjustments and corrective actions if results do not align with expectations.

1.3.1. Advertising

Advertising involves promoting the project to a wider audience. Effective advertising helps raise awareness, attract stakeholders, and generate interest in the project. Strategies included in advertising are the project brand identity, including logo, the project brochure, poster and roll-up banner, videos and podcasts.

1.3.1.1. Project Brand Identity

The project brand identity refers to the visual and conceptual elements that represent the project. This includes the project's name, logo, colour scheme, typography, and overall design style. A strong brand identity helps create a memorable and recognizable image for the project, making it easier for stakeholders to connect with and trust the project. It also ensures consistency across all communication materials, reinforcing the project's values and goals.

AI-EFFECT identity conveys innovation, futurism, and modernity, adding a more contemporary and progressive vision.

For more details see Appendix A – Project Brand Identity

1.3.1.2. Logo

The logo represents the project visually, conveying project's mission and objectives. It is used on all project-related materials, including websites, social media, presentations, helping to establish a cohesive image.

AI-EFFECT main logo is made up of three elements:

1. **The symbol.** It combines several symbols that summarize the values and history of the brand:
 - a. The cube structure represents the testing facility's stability, where various technologies and data undergo testing, validation, and analysis.
 - b. The AI circuits are symbolized by dots and lines, illustrating the integration of artificial intelligence with sustainability to optimize and manage energy solutions.
 - c. The leaf represents energy sustainability, emphasizing AI-EFFECT's mission to promote eco-friendly energy solutions and advance the global energy transition.
 - d. The data and digital representation which, the leaf is shaped into a cube, symbolizing the digital analysis within the platform, showcasing the blend of sustainability and technology to innovate in the energy sector.
2. **Typography (AI-EFFECT).** The main typography is SUSE font, which serves as the basis for all communication. It is minimal, futuristic with trends linked to innovation. TREBUCHET MS was defined as a complementary typography to the Trebuchet family, as it is a system font, available on all computers. This typography should be used when it is not possible to use the institutional typography.
3. **Signature/motto.** Driving Energy Transition Through AI Experimentation. It encapsulates the vision of transforming the energy sector through innovative AI solutions, promoting sustainability, and fostering collaboration for a better future.
4. **Chromatic Palette.** The Blue is linked to technology and innovation, while the green is associated with sustainability. The gradient represents the synergy between innovation and sustainability, underscoring the interconnectedness of these elements in addressing global challenges such as climate change and energy security.

The logo and its elements are represented in Figure 1, Figure 2 and Figure 3.

Figure 1 Logo symbology

<p>MAIN COLOR</p> <p>#3C3EE1 R60 G62 B225 C82 M76 Y0 KO PANTONE 2728 C/U</p>	<p>SECONDARY COLOR</p> <p>#A1FFD6 R161 G255 B214 C32 M0 Y27 KO PANTONE 331 C / U</p>	<p>GRADIENT</p> <p>#3C3EE1 + A1FFD6</p>	<p>SECONDARY COLOR</p> <p>#FFFFFF R255 G255 B255 C0 M0 Y0 KO</p>
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Figure 2 Chromatic Palette

Figure 3 Different logo representations

1.3.1.3. Flyer and roll-up banner

The flyer provides detailed information about the project, including its objectives, benefits, and key features. It is designed to be informative and visually appealing, making it easy for stakeholders to understand the project's value.

The roll-up banner can be used at events and conferences to promote the project. It features key messages and an infographic, designed to attract, and inform passersby about the project's goals and structure. The flyer and roll-up banner are in the Appendix B – Flyer and Roll-Up Banner.

These materials are essential for effective communication and promotion, helping to raise awareness and engage with various audiences.

1.3.2. Videos

This initial video of the project introduces the AI-EFFECT project, briefly explaining what the AI-EFFECT project is about, highlight the significance of the project in the context of energy transition and AI experimentation. The video is a blend of stock footage and graphic animation, lasting approximately 1 minute and 30 seconds, with a narrator guiding the audience through the content.

This video serves as a compelling introduction to the AI-EFFECT project, effectively communicating its vision and engaging all targeted audiences. The video was produced and disseminated through project channels in M5.

In addition to this video, at least two more will be produced, focused on the demonstration nodes and project results.

Figure 4 Screenshots from the project video.

1.3.2.1. Podcast

Podcasts are an impactful way to promote the AI-EFFECT project and engage a wide-ranging audience. To amplify AI-EFFECT's reach, the well-established EPRI Current podcast will host special episodes dedicated to the project. These episodes will feature AI-EFFECT's unique branding and focus on delivering in-depth insights, updates, and discussions about the project's progress and its impact, fostering greater awareness and engagement.

The objectives of the podcast are:

- **Build Awareness:** Educate and inform the audience about AI in the energy sector.
- **Provide Updates:** Keep listeners informed about project progress and milestones.
- **Engage Target Audience:** Connect with organizations and individuals with varying levels of expertise and interest in AI and energy.
- **Communicate with TEF Members:** Share knowledge about AI testing and validation, and discuss ethical issues.

1.3.2.2. Podcast Overview

- **Number of Episodes:** 6
- **Guests per Episode:** 2 or 3
- **Maximum Duration per Episode:** 25 minutes
- **Distribution Channels:** Project channels and podbean

This approach not only enhances visibility but also fosters a deeper connection with the audience, ensuring the project's goals and achievements are widely recognized and supported.

The podcasts are planned according to the timeline on Table 6.

Table 6 Provisional outline of the six project podcast episodes

Episode	Publishing date	Topics to cover
1	April 2025	Introduction to AI and AI in the Energy Sector: Overview of the project and its use cases.
2	September/ October 2025	Project Framework and Architecture
3	March/April 2026	Other TEFs/sister projects discussion
4	September/October 2026	Project Demonstration Nodes
5	March / April 2027	Data and AI policies in Europe
6	September 2027	Project outcomes and lessons learned

The line up for the first episode is as follows:

1. Introduction to AI

- Explaining/demystifying the concept of AI. Providing more information on the EU context, like AI Act and energy critical infrastructures (EEU)
- How can/is AI being applied in the energy sector in Europe? (ENEL)
- What are the needs of the industry that AI can address? (ENEL)
- Can you share any specific examples of how AI is currently being used in your organization? (ENEL)
- What are some of the key benefits and challenges of integrating AI into the energy sector? (EEU/ENEL)

2. Overview of the AI-EFFECT Project

- What drove the AI-EFFECT project, and what are its main goals? (EEU)
- How does the project aim to address current challenges in the energy sector (mention infrastructures and AI ACT)? (EEU/ENEL)
- How can we ensure the broad applicability of AI-EFFECT applications? (DTU)

3. Introduction to Project Use Cases

- Can you provide an overview of the use cases being developed under the AI-EFFECT project? (DTU)
- What impact do you anticipate these use cases will have on the energy sector? (DTU)
- What challenges have been identified that the AI-EFFECT architecture needs to address efficiently? (DTU)

4. Conclusion: project future steps (EEU)

1.3.3. Public Relations

1.3.3.1. Press Releases

Press releases are part of the public relations efforts. Media outlets play a crucial and credible role in engaging with a wider audience. Consequently, the project aims to distribute at least 8 press releases (PRs), achieving a total of 25 media insertions. The first release, issued in M2, announced the project's commencement and is documented in Appendix C – Press Release. This release was sent to media outlets in Ireland, Italy and Portugal. Details of the press release insertions in the media are summarized in Table 7.

Table 7 Project initial press release insertions in the media

Geographic range	Media Outlet	Title & Link
Ireland	Irish Tech News	Advancing AI Integration in the European Energy Sector

	Silicon Republic	Dublin’s EPRI leads European project to advance AI use in the energy sector
Portugal	Opinio Publica	Avançar com a Integração da IA no Setor de Energia Europeu: CEVE Participa no Projeto AI-EFFECT como Piloto Português
European	Smart Energy International	Project AI-EFFECT to establish energy sector AI use cases
	Open PR	Advancing AI Integration in the European Energy Sector
	Euractiv	Commission working on study to develop AI model energy efficiency framework
	Energy Central	Advancing AI Integration in the European Energy Sector

In an effort to amplify the project reach, some partners have also published information on other online channels, as shown in Table 8.

Table 8 Other online channels disseminating project information

Channel	Link
TU DELFT website	https://www.tudelft.nl/en/2024/eemcs/advancing-ai-integration-in-the-european-energy-sector
EEU website	https://europe.epri.com/project/ai-effect
RWTH website	https://www.acs.eonerc.rwth-aachen.de/cms/e-on-erc-ac/forschung/forschungsprojekte/modeling-simulation-and-hil-methods/~bkqbfv/ai-effect/?lidx=1

1.3.3.2. Events

Events serve as a crucial platform to engage with the project audience, exchange knowledge, and share findings. The project will actively promote presentations at leading scientific conferences and participate in EU and industry events, fairs, and exhibitions. The project’s strategy includes attending events organized by experts, researchers, clients, and industry audiences, where project partners will be invited to present their work and vision.

In addition to attending events, the project will organize training workshops and webinars. These will target various stakeholder groups to inform them about the benefits, best practices, and specific adaptations of the project. The sessions will cater to both technical/managerial staff and the general public/consumers.

AI-EFFECT will foster collaboration between policymakers, researchers, standardization bodies, and industry stakeholders to co-design frameworks that incentivize, boost, and support the adoption of AI-powered tools and solutions in the energy sector. This collaborative approach ensures that policies are well-informed, practical, and aligned with the needs of all stakeholders.

AI-EFFECT will establish knowledge-sharing initiatives, such as webinars, conferences, and online forums, to facilitate dialogue and information exchange among policymakers, researchers, industry stakeholders, and citizens. These initiatives will provide opportunities for continuous learning, dissemination of best

practices, and networking among stakeholders, fostering a collaborative ecosystem for policy development and implementation.

The project will participate in:

- **EU and Industry Events, Fairs, and Exhibitions:** Including EU Innovation Days, Enlit Europe, European Sustainable Energy Week (EUSEW), Innogrid, CIRED, and IEEE T&D.
- **Joint Meetings and Clustering:** With other EU consortia under the umbrella of the REPowerEU initiative and other European workgroups.
- **Site Visits and Demonstrations:** Direct demonstrations of outcomes at demo sites.

Until M6 the project has been represented in three events:

1. RTE AI Day, 18th November 2024, France
2. Artificial Intelligence (AI) & Digital Transformation (DX) in Electric Power Summit, 7th-9th January 2025, California, USA
3. E.DSO Future Grid Innovation Summit, 6th February 2025, Brussels, Belgium

1.3.4. Digital Marketing

1.3.4.1. Website

A dedicated website has been developed at www.ai-effect.eu (Homepage, n.d.) to showcase the project's activities and share its outcomes. Visitors to the website can find:

- Detailed information about the project, including its challenges, goals and expected impact.
- Insights into each demonstration node.
- Access to valuable resources such as deliverables, scientific papers, and other materials related to AI-EFFECT's progress and results.
- The latest news and updates on project-related events.
- Contact information for further inquiries.

The website is structured as follows:

1. **Homepage** – Highlights the project tagline, demonstration nodes, and recent updates.
2. **About the project** – Provides context, objectives, benefits, and impact.
3. **Demonstration and validation** – Details the objectives, specifics, and expected impacts of each demo node.
4. **Resources** – Contains all technical outputs of the project, including deliverables, reports, scientific publications, technical presentations and factsheets.
5. **Meet the Consortium** – Information about the project partners.
6. **Communications** – Features news, events, communication materials, project newsletters and podcast episodes.
7. **Contacts** – Includes a form for sending messages to the project coordinator.

The website has its own Content Management System (CMS) and integrates the project's LinkedIn. It features a subscription form for the project newsletter. Website traffic and downloads are being monitored using Matomo Analytics, an open-source platform endorsed by the European Commission. This tool provides anonymized yet insightful data on user behaviour, ensuring compliance with the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The website was launched in M3 and it aims to achieve 1500 visits annually.

A screenshot of the website homepage is provided in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Screenshot of the website homepage

1.3.4.2. Social Media

The project has selected LinkedIn as its primary social media platforms. The LinkedIn page (AI-EFFECT LinkedIn Page, n.d.) will be instrumental in informing and engaging primarily with research, academia, and the energy industry Social media, but overall, being a free and accessible tool with a diverse audience, LinkedIn will enable the project to reach the public sphere, thereby raising awareness among a broader audience that includes all key target groups.

Social media activities will be conducted bi-weekly and will comply with the project visual identity in order to maintain consistency, which is crucial for driving reach and engagement. The content shared will follow the strategy and timeframe highlighted for each communication campaign described in the next chapter of this deliverable. Therefore, at this stage, the content shared on social media has covered the project's context, objectives, benefits, consortium, and foreseen impact, raising awareness and providing essential information.

The impact of these efforts will be tracked using the analytics tools provided by LinkedIn. Growth in followers and impressions will serve as indicators of the project's reach and influence, while engagement will measure the effectiveness of the content in fostering active participation. The goal is to achieve at least three hundred impressions and ten engagements per post.

Figure 6 shows a screenshot of the project's page on LinkedIn.

Figure 6 Screenshot of the project's pages on LinkedIn.

1.3.5. Direct Marketing

1.3.5.1. Newsletter

The newsletter will directly engage project stakeholders. It will follow a structured template, including:

- **Cover Story:** Featuring a major milestone, outcome, or news item, accompanied by visuals such as photos, infographics, or videos.
- **News & Events:** Summarizing recent activities and providing previews of upcoming events.
- **Resources:** Offering links to valuable materials and resources related to the project.
- **Scientific Publications:** Sharing updates on recent publications and research findings.
- **Public Deliverables & Reports:** Providing access to project deliverables and additional reports.
- **Communication Materials:** Detailing promotional materials developed for the project.
- **Contacts, Acknowledgments, and Unsubscribe Option.**

It will be managed and distributed through a digital marketing platform, and LinkedIn Newsletters platform. The newsletter will be sent to all subscribers twice a year. It can be subscribed via the footer of the project website. The first edition will be released in April 2025.

1.4. Communication Campaigns

The AI-EFFECT project will be developed through four separate phases, mapped to the project objectives:

- 1) **Use cases and test methodology and node development (M1-16).** This phase involves developing the four AI focussed use cases in the four demonstration nodes with the IT infrastructure with a testing methodology.
- 2) **Framework and architecture design (M6-24).** This phase involves development of the architecture, for the hardware and software solution platform leveraging pre-existing infrastructure and facilities and EU dataspace components.
- 3) **Solution development, testing and node demonstration (M6-36):** From the architecture -the AI-EFFECT digital solution will be built using modular digital services and data spaces building blocks. The AI-EFFECT architecture, deployed in the four nodes, will then be used to test and demonstrate the solution.
- 4) **Develop the enduring model for AI-EFFECT (M6-36).** Develop the strategy, explore the regulatory landscape, and develop the enduring model in line with the EU AI Act and other regulations and legal requirements. This will be in collaboration with the other consortium members, and other EU TEFs.

The communication plan will be divided into five different campaigns, consistent with the four separate phases of the project described in the project methodology, with one more added at the beginning for initial awareness. The five campaigns aim to focus on specific developments at a time, thus leveraging project awareness and impact.

- 1) Initial Awareness (M1-M9)
- 2) Use Cases (M09-M16)
- 3) Framework and Architecture (M9-M24)
- 4) Nodes demonstration (M25- M36)
- 5) Enduring Model and Final outcomes (M30-M38)

This approach ensures that communication efforts are strategically phased to maximize impact and engagement throughout the AI-EFFECT project. Each campaign is synchronized with key project milestones and deliverables, ensuring stakeholders are informed and engaged at critical stages of technological development, pilot testing, and market integration. The campaigns will be updated in future deliverables.

1.4.1. Campaign 1: Initial Awareness

Objectives:

- Introduce AI-EFFECT project to key stakeholders and the general public with tailored messages.
- Create awareness about the project's goals, significance, and expected outcomes.
- Establish a foundation for ongoing engagement and support throughout the project.

Key Activities:

- Website and Social Media Launch: Create a project website and establish social media profiles to provide updates, share resources, and interact with stakeholders.
- Press Releases and Media Outreach: Issue press releases and collaborate with media outlets to attract coverage and spark interest in the project.
- Launch of Videos and Communication Materials and channels: Release essential video and materials, including flyers, roll-up banners, and other graphics, to support project communication. Issue first episode podcast providing an overview of the project and first newsletter.
- Stakeholder Engagement: Reach out to target groups (scientific communities, industry, policymakers) through targeted emails, newsletters, and direct communications.

Target Groups:

All

Timeline:

Months 1-9

1.4.2. Campaign 2: Use Cases Development

Objectives:

- Raise Awareness: Inform stakeholders about the design and implementation of AI-EFFECT use cases, operating framework, and validation tools.
- Educate: Provide detailed information on the functionalities, interfaces, and certification processes involved.
- Collaboration: Mutual share of use cases and datasets with research and academia.

Key Activities:

- Develop Open Education resources such as flyers and graphics to explain the AI-EFFECT functionalities and framework.
- Organize interactive sessions to demonstrate the use cases and toolbox developed, such as workshops or webinars.

Target Groups

- TG1: Scientific Communities, R&D and Academia.
- TG2 Energy Industry
- TG4 Technology Providers

Timeline:

- Months 9-16

1.4.3. Campaign 3: Framework and Architecture

Objectives:

- Inform: Raise awareness about the design and implementation of the modular architecture for the Cyber-Physical aspects of AI-EFFECT.
- Educate: Provide detailed information on technical requirements, hardware and software tools, and performance criteria.

Key activities:

- Content Development: Create detailed materials such as videos, infographics, and technical documents explaining the modular architecture and its components.
- Workshops and Webinars: Host sessions to demonstrate the architecture, interconnection solutions, and data safety tools.
- Engage: with other TEFs and BRIDGE Initiative to gather insights and ensure alignment.

Target Groups

- TG1: Scientific Communities, R&D and Academia.
- TG2 Energy Industry
- TG4 Technology Providers

Timeline:

- Months 9-24

1.4.4. Campaign 4: Nodes demonstration

Objectives:

- Inform: Raise awareness about the project nodes, its objectives and specificities.
- Educate: Provide detailed information on technical requirements, hardware and software tools, and performance criteria.

Key activities:

- Content Development: Create detailed materials such as videos, infographics showcasing the nodes.
- Stakeholder Engagement: Promote site visits and demonstrations of outcomes at demo sites.
- Media outreach: promote demonstrations outcomes within the media and general public.

Target Groups

- TG1: Scientific Communities, R&D and Academia.
- TG2 Energy Industry
- TG3: Non-profit Organisations
- TG4 Technology Providers
- TG5: Media and General Public

Timeline:

- Months 25-36

1.4.5. Campaign 5: Project Sustainability and Final Results

Objectives:

- Communicate the final results, outcomes, and achievements of the AI-EFFECT project.
- Highlight the impact and benefits of project innovations on stakeholders and the energy sector.
- Facilitate the uptake and utilization of project results by stakeholders.

Key Activities:

- Results Dissemination: Publish comprehensive reports, case studies, and white papers summarizing the project's findings, innovations, and outcomes. Make these available through the project website, social media channels, and targeted distribution to stakeholders.
- Showcase Events: Organize a final showcase event, conference, or webinar to present key findings, success stories, and demonstrations of project innovations. Invite stakeholders, policymakers, industry representatives, and the general public.
- Facilitate the uptake and utilization of project results by stakeholders.
- Engage with Industry, policymakers and standardization bodies to develop recommendations for policy makers to ensure viability for AI-EFFECT and to ensure governance and business models for an enduring project model.

Target Groups

All

Timeline:

- Months -30-36, ensuring results uptake beyond the project lifetime

Figure 7 Summarizes the timeline for the 5 communication campaigns.

Figure 7 Summary of the 5 Communication Campaigns

1.5. Dissemination activities

In the project, alongside communication activities, targeted dissemination actions will be implemented to ensure the project generates further impact, supports future research, and opens up potential business opportunities.

1.5.1. Cooperation with other TEFs and initiatives

AI-EFFECT will engage with European and global energy sector stakeholders and asset owners to curate use cases, training, and test data, and to match concepts and ideas to viable datasets.

Engagement with other EU Testing and Experimentation Facilities (TEFs) inside and outside the energy sector will be particularly relevant for knowledge sharing, cross-pollination and technology and regulations standardisation, reducing capital investment and development costs, and ensuring the project sustainability beyond its lifetime.

Engagement will go beyond Europe, reaching international partners and equivalents in USA, Canada, Australia, Middle East, South America, and Asia to establish collaborative opportunities.

The project will also promote clustering activities and meetings with other EU consortia under the umbrella of the *REPowerEU* initiative and other European workgroups, such as BRIDGE Initiative.

This collaborative approach ensures that AI-EFFECT contributes to the broader ecosystem, fostering innovation, standardization, and cost-efficiency in the energy sector.

The project reached out to a few other TEFs with initial meetings taking place. One of these TEFs is CoordinaTEF. This project aims TEFs to foster the widespread adoption of AI technologies across various industries, supporting SMEs and businesses in bringing AI-based technologies from the lab to the market. The AI-EFFECT project will progress with planning joint dissemination activities with CoordinaTEF.

1.5.2. Scientific Publications

AI-EFFECT project is committed to fully supporting open science practices, The project will actively pursue Open Access (OA) publishing, using a dedicated budget for Gold OA and leveraging transformative agreements for Green OA. The project will utilize open access publishing venues such as Open Research Europe and public open access repositories compatible with OpenAIRE, including Zenodo and the institutional repositories of consortium members. The publication of project results in peer-reviewed journals will be strongly encouraged, aiming for at least 10 open access journal publications. Additionally, the project plans to deliver 12 presentations at top scientific conferences and participate in various academic and industry events, fairs, and exhibitions. All publications will have an indication of the acknowledgment and disclaimer in the referring to the project:

AI-EFFECT is supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under agreement 101172952. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The targeted journals include potentially include IEEE Transactions and journals, ENERGY, SEGAN, IJEPES, EPSR.

The presentations in scientific conferences include PSCC, IEEE PowerTech, SEST, IEEE PES GM, IEEE IECON, IEEE MELECON, IEEE EUROCON, UPEC, IEEE INDIN, EEEIC, IEEE IAS, ISGT, EEM, CCTA and HICSS.

Notably, 20 out of the 25 project deliverables will have a Public (PU) dissemination level, meaning 95% of the deliverables will be publicly accessible, which is significant.

Project materials, including deliverables, open access publications, and general information, will be available on the project website. These materials will be regularly updated and promoted through the project's communication channels, engaging all relevant target groups, including citizens, civil society, and end-users, in the co-creation process of innovation agendas.

1.5.3. Workshops, Webinars and Open Educational Resources

The project will organise workshops and webinars to provide hands-on training on the solutions developed and foster collaboration and knowledge sharing between participants and initiatives.

The Open Educational Resources (OER) will support education and training on the functionalities and framework developed as part of the project. These include technical sheets, infographics, videos and other materials.

1.5.4. Site visits

The project aims to actively involve stakeholders by showcasing the practical applications and benefits of the AI-EFFECT project through site visits and live demonstrations. These will enhance their understanding of the project's impact and foster a collaborative environment that supports the successful implementation and scaling of the AI technologies.

1.5.5. Replication Advisory Group

The Replication Advisory Group will foster replication beyond the consortium. This activity is linked with WP5 Task 5.1 Strategic objectives and roadmap for the short-, medium-, and long-term viability of AI-EFFECT. This task is only set to commence on Month 6 and will detail the replication plan, including the strategy and roadmap. AI-EFFECT will also form a Replication and Exploitation Board = with key stakeholder representatives from the consortium. This board will guide the project towards market needs and help transfer results to the market.

Table 9 outlines the KPIs for each dissemination activity.

Table 9 Dissemination KPIs and Target Values

Dissemination Activities and Channels	TGs	KPI
Publications in peer-reviewed OA scientific journals, potentially including IEEE Transactions and journals, ENERGY, SEGAN, IJEPES, EPSR.	TG1, TG2	> 10 OA journal publications
Presentations in high profile scientific conferences.	TG1, TG2	> 12 presentations, reaching > 1000 academics
EU and Industry events, Fairs and Exhibitions , including EU Innovation Days, Enlit, EUSEW, Innogrid, CIRED, and IEEE T&D	TG2, TG6	> 6 events, > 600 experts
Joint Meetings and clustering with other EU consortia under the umbrella of the <i>REPowerEU</i> initiative and other European workgroups	TG2, TG3, TG5	> 5 cooperations > 3 joint meetings
Standards, Technical Committees and Regulations contributions	TG6, TG7	> 3 contributions
Replication Advisory Group establishment to foster replication beyond the consortium	TG2, TG4, TG6, TG7	> 5 members from all partner countries
Site Visits or other forms of direct demonstration of outcomes at demo sites	TG4, TG6, TG7	> 10 companies > 100 visitors
Best Practices and Recommendations Manual for industry and policymakers	TG2, TG6	> 1 handbook
Workshops, Webinars and Open Educational Resources (OER)	TG1, TG2	> 5 workshops or webinars; > 3 OER

2. Conclusion

The AI-EFFECT project is poised to drive energy transition through AI experimentation.

The D6.3 Initial Dissemination and Communication Plan, as detailed in this report, acts as a comprehensive guide to ensure the project's visibility, engagement, and impact. By outlining clear strategies, tools, and campaigns, this deliverable establishes the foundation for effective communication and dissemination efforts throughout the project's lifecycle and beyond.

Continuous monitoring and updating of this plan will be essential to adapt to the project's progress and ensure that its objectives—enhancing stakeholder awareness, trust, and participation in AI advancements—are fully achieved. Consequently, and as a follow up of this deliverable, interim and final report on dissemination and communication activities, stakeholder's engagement, and project's outreach (D6.4 Dissemination, communication, and outreach activities) are planned for M18 and M36.

Ultimately, the AI-EFFECT project aims to boost efficiency, resilience, and sustainability in the European energy ecosystem, by integrating AI into critical energy infrastructure.

3. References

AI-EFFECT LinkedIn Page. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.linkedin.com/company/ai-effect-project>
Homepage. (n.d.). Retrieved from AI-EFFECT: <https://ai-effect.eu/>

4. Appendix

Appendix A – Project Brand Identity

BRAND GUIDELINES AI-EFFECT

Welcome to the AI-EFFECT graphic Identity manual.

Our graphic identity is highly important for the unity of our brand. In this sense, this manual was prepared with the aim of defining and standardizing AI-EFFECT corporate image and clarifying any doubts that may arise during its application and use.

All rules defined in this manual must be respected, without exception. Compliance with these standards makes it possible to reinforce the personality of our brand and ensure a cohesive image.

LOGO

The AI-EFFECT logo brings together all the brand's values.

It is geometric, minimal and has great application flexibility in the media and supports where the brand moves.

AI-EFFECT Identity conveys innovation, futurism and modernity, adding a more contemporary and progressive vision.

AI·EFFECT

LOGO LOGO ELEMENTS

The main logo is made up of three elements:

The symbol, typography (AI-EFFECT) and signature.

All elements must live together in accordance with the rules presented in this manual, except for the exceptions provided above.

The main typography is minimal, futuristic with trends linked to innovation.

SYMBOL

+

AI·EFFECT

MAIN TYPOGRAPHY

+

Driving Energy Transition
Through AI Experimentation

DESCRIPTIVE

LOGO SIMBOLOGY

This combines several symbols that summarize the values and history of the brand:

Firstly, to build the logo and its entire concept, we have the **cube structure** that represents the testing facility's stability, where various technologies and data undergo testing, validation, and analysis. Then we have **AI circuits** symbolized by dots and lines, illustrating the integration of artificial intelligence with sustainability to optimize and manage energy solutions. In the center to the logo, we have **the leaf** represents energy sustainability, emphasizing AI-EFFECT's mission to promote eco-friendly energy solutions and advance the global energy transition. And finally the **data and digital** representation with, the leaf is shaped into a cube, symbolizing the digital analysis within the platform, showcasing the blend of sustainability and technology to innovate in the energy sector.

Testing Facilities

+

Artificial Intelligence

+

Energy Sustainability

+

Digital Data

=

LOGO LOGO VERSIONS

MAIN VERSION

There are 4 versions of the logo, with the main version appearing immediately above. If your reading is in question, or due to some limitation in the production of the media, the secondary versions of the same, represented on this page, may be used.

NOTE: All versions have their respective monochrome version.

SECONDARY VERSION 01

This is a secondary version of the logo with the symbol and signature aligned to the left. It may be used when the readability conditions of the main version are not ensured (e.g. printing or application in small sizes).

SECONDARY VERSION 02

This is a version with lettering only. It can be used when the legibility conditions of the main version are not guaranteed (e.g. printing in small sizes).

SECONDARY VERSION 03

This is the logo symbol. It may be used freely in all media and applications, but never as a replacement for the main logo.

LOGO SAFETY MARGINS

So that the logo always maintains legibility, a safety area was created around it that must protect it from any other elements.

To make this calculation easy, an element of the logo was chosen — the letter 'A' (Capital Letter), which defines the proportions of the safety margins.

LOGO ALIGNMENT

Taking into account the general alignment of the entire logo composition, it should always be aligned to the left or center, and never to the right. The only exception may apply when the logo is placed vertically, as shown in the examples below.

BRAND GUIDELINES / AI-EFFECT

LOGO MINIMUM DIMENSIONS

When applying the logo in the most varied media, it is necessary to take into account its minimum dimensions, so that it has the necessary legibility for comfortable reading without major difficulties.

Below are the minimum sizes reproduction of the various versions.

VERSÃO PRINCIPAL
COM SÍMBOLO E ASSINATURA
30MM

VERSÃO SECUNDÁRIA
60MM

VERSÃO SECUNDÁRIA
25MM

VERSÃO SECUNDÁRIA
(SÍMBOLO)
10MM

BRAND GUIDELINES / AI-EFFECT

CHROMATIC PALETTE

<p>MAIN COLOR</p> <p>#3C3EE1 R60 G62 B225 CB2 M76 Y0 K0 PANTONE Z728 C/U</p>	<p>SECONDARY COLOR</p> <p>#A1FFD6 R161 G255 B214 C32 M0 Y27 K0 PANTONE 331 C / U</p>	<p>GRADIENT</p> <p>#3C3EE1 + A1FFD6</p>	<p>SECONDARY COLOR</p> <p>#FFFFFF R255 G255 B255 CO M0 Y0 K0</p>
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CHROMATIC PALETTE BEHAVIORS UNDER CHROMATIC BACKGROUNDS

Preferably, the logo should be applied on light backgrounds or institutional colors. If this is not possible, you must make readability a priority. In the following examples, the logo assumes its behavior in color, or in negative, depending on the respective background.

AI-EFFECT	AI-EFFECT	AI-EFFECT	AI-EFFECT	AI-EFFECT	AI-EFFECT
AI-EFFECT	AI-EFFECT	AI-EFFECT	AI-EFFECT	AI-EFFECT	AI-EFFECT
AI-EFFECT	AI-EFFECT	AI-EFFECT	AI-EFFECT	AI-EFFECT	AI-EFFECT

17 BRAND GUIDELINES / AI-EFFECT

CHROMATIC PALETTE BEHAVIORS UNDER PHOTOGRAPHIC BACKGROUNDS

The application of the logo on photographic backgrounds must respect the principles of legibility. You should look for a frame in which there is sufficient contrast between the background and the logo and preferably on flat spots.

Note: On photographic backgrounds, only monochromatic logos should be used.

INCORRECTIONS

Below are some examples of how not to use/apply the logo. These examples are valid for all existing versions.

CHANGE THE
CHROMATIC ORDER

USE OTHER TYPOGRAPHY
IN REPLACEMENT

USE OUTLINES, TRANSPARENCIES,
WATERMARKS OR ANY GRAPHIC ENHANCEMENT.

USE OTHER COLOR SCHEMES THAT ARE
NOT PROVIDED FOR IN THIS MANUAL

DISTORT IDENTITY

DISRESPECT THE DIMENSIONS
PROVIDED FOR THE SAFETY
MARGINS

INSTITUTIONAL TYPOGRAPHY MAIN

SUSE

The SUSE font serves as the basis for all communication. Some weights were chosen from his family for current use in graphic pieces, but all weights can be used. This font is available on Google Fonts.

SUSE LIGHT

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
QRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrs
tuvwxyz
0123456789!/?#/. ,

SUSE MEDIUM

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
QRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrs
tuvwxyz
0123456789!/?#/. ,

SUSE REGULAR

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
QRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrs
tuvwxyz
0123456789!/?#/. ,

SUSE BOLD

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
QRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrs
tuvwxyz
0123456789!/?#/. ,

BRAND GUIDELINES / AI-EFFECT

INSTITUTIONAL TYPOGRAPHY ALTERNATIVE

TREBUCHET MS

It was defined as a complementary typography to the Trebuchet family, as it is a system font, available on all computers. This typography should be used when it is not possible to use the Institutional typography.

TREBUCHET MS REGULAR

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
STUVWXYZ
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
STUVWXYZ
0123456789!/?#/. ,

TREBUCHET BOLD

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
STUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrst
uvwxyz
0123456789!/?#/. ,

BRAND GUIDELINES / AI-EFFECT

GRAPHIC IDENTITY

OTHER BRAND GRAPHIC ELEMENTS

On this page and the next ones, there are some images where it is possible to observe the application of the brand's visual identity in the most varied media, in a generalized way.

16 BRAND GUIDELINES / AI-EFFECT

GRAPHIC IDENTITY

OTHER BRAND GRAPHIC ELEMENTS

17 BRAND GUIDELINES / AI-EFFECT

Appendix B – Flyer and Roll-Up Banner

Project Outcomes

A working TEF for AI applications for the energy sector utilising a modular, scalable node-based architecture and accessible digital platform.

Framework for testing and validating AI applications, including risk assessment, testing methodologies for AI applications that can be generalised to all use cases.

The AI-EFFECT concept will be replicated across Europe with additional nodes, turning AI into a real enabler of the energy transition.

Consortium

The project runs from October 2024 to September 2027. It brings together 19 leading European organisations, under the coordination of EPRI Europe.

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AI-EFFECT is supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under agreement 101172952. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Context

As the digital age transforms the energy landscape, the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and critical energy infrastructure is set to boost efficiency, resilience, and sustainability.

The project AI-EFFECT (Artificial Intelligence Experimentation Facility For the Energy seCTOR) is an European funded project, aiming to address:

The need to link utilities that have data streams and datasets and major challenges to the AI industry and research communities who have the tools and capabilities to solve the utility challenges.

The need for a consistent, standardised approach to development of trustworthy AI for the energy sector.

The need to standardise and certify solutions based on a security and risk framework, in compliance with the EU AI Act.

AI-EFFECT will establish a European Testing and Experimentation Facility (TEF) for AI applications in the energy sector, enabling development, testing, and validation at various stages. It will virtually connect existing European computer and lab facilities through a digital platform, ensuring interoperability, scalability, and secure data exchange.

Project Objectives

Demonstration Nodes:

The project will develop four demonstration nodes in Denmark, the Netherlands, Portugal, and Germany, each focusing on specific use cases:

Danish Node

District Heating and Sector Coupling

Dutch Node

Transmission System Congestion Management

German Node

DER Integration in Distribution System

Portuguese Node

Energy Community Data Space

AI-EFFECT

DRIVING ENERGY TRANSITION THROUGH AI EXPERIMENTATION

AI-EFFECT will establish a **European Testing and Experimentation Facility (TEF)** for AI applications in the energy sector, enabling **development, testing, and validation** at various stages. It will virtually connect existing European computer and lab facilities through a digital platform, ensuring **interoperability, scalability, and secure data exchange**.

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AI-EFFECT is supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under agreement 101172952. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Appendix C – Press Release

Advancing AI Integration in the European Energy Sector

Dublin, 07 November 2024 - As the digital age transforms the energy landscape, the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and critical energy infrastructure could boost efficiency, resilience, and sustainability. To drive this innovation, Dublin-based EPRI Europe is launching AI-EFFECT, aimed at accelerating the development, testing, and validation of AI applications in the energy sector.

AI-EFFECT brings together 19 leading European organisations spanning research institutions, energy operators, and academia, including transmission and distribution system operators Enel and TenneT.

The three-year project will develop four demonstrations across Europe—Denmark, the Netherlands, Portugal, and Germany—each addressing a distinct use case, including multi-energy systems, congestion management, energy efficiency, and DER (Distributed Energy Resources) integration. The aim of the project is to establish a European AI Testing and Experimentation Facility (TEF) for the energy sector, enabling development, testing, and validation at various stages. It will virtually connect existing European computer and lab facilities through a digital platform.

“This project will create a unique digital platform that helps both the AI industry and energy utilities in Europe to work together to develop and use AI in the energy industry. By making energy systems smarter, more efficient, and more reliable, we’re directly supporting decarbonization efforts and advancing EPRI Europe’s mission of driving innovation to ensure a cleaner, more resilient energy future,” said Eamonn Lannoye, EPRI Europe managing director.

AI-EFFECT’s innovative digital platform will drive European collaboration by enabling secure data sharing, AI model development, testing and validation, and seamless integration with the EU data spaces framework. AI has broad energy applications including forecasting energy demand, network anomaly detection, simulation, and reporting automation. The AI-EFFECT platform will help ensure that these AI tools are tested securely before deployment on real-world systems, following European data-sharing rules.

“As a global leader in the energy sector, we are extremely pleased to be part of the AI-EFFECT project, harnessing the power of artificial intelligence to facilitate the energy transition. We expect that this initiative will drive innovation and significantly enhance the efficiency and the intrinsic security of energy systems across Europe. Enel is actively sharing its global expertise and real-life scenarios, aiming to improve the quality of life through increasingly innovative, and responsible energy solutions,” said Gianni Vittorio Armani, head of Enel grids and Innovability.

AI-EFFECT aims to position Europe at the forefront of AI integration in the energy sector, offering a robust, secure, and scalable platform to foster innovation, through research, demonstration, and collaboration. The project will also address key regulatory challenges, including compliance with the EU AI Act, ensuring AI systems for energy are transparent, secure, reliable, and interpretable.

AI-EFFECT will run until September 2027 and is funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe program, under agreement no. 101172952. The full consortium is composed of: EPRI Europe, [Maynooth University](#) and [IKIM](#) (Ireland); [INESC TEC](#), [WATT-IS](#) and [CEVE](#) (Portugal); [DTU](#), [Bornholms Energi & Forsyning](#) and [CDK](#) (Denmark); [Fraunhofer FIT](#), [RWTH Aachen University](#) and [Hertie School](#) (Germany); [TUDelft](#) and [Tennet](#) (Netherlands); [IRTSX](#) (France); [DNV](#) (Norway); [EnliteAI](#) (Austria); [ENEL](#) (Italy); and [EDRD](#) (Spain).

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